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THE ROLE OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMUNICATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE BUSINESS MODEL IN THE BEAUTY INDUSTRY

РОЛЬ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙНИХ КОМУНІКАЦІЙ У РОЗВИТКУ СЕРВІСНОЇ МОДЕЛІ БІЗНЕСУ ІНДУСТРІЇ КРАСИ

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Нямецук Г.В., Крупський О.П., Стасюк Ю.М. Роль організаційних комунікацій у розвитку сервісної моделі бізнесу індустрії краси. Оглядова стаття.

У статті досліджено роль організаційних комунікацій як чинника розвитку сервісної моделі бізнесу в індустрії краси. Розкрито значення внутрішньої та зовнішньої комунікації для забезпечення якісної взаємодії з клієнтами, стабільності сервісних процесів і підтримки брендової ідентичності. Визначено основні напрями впливу комунікацій: стандартизацію послуг, узгодженість інформаційних потоків, адаптивність персоналу та персоналізацію клієнтського досвіду. Наголошено на стратегічній ролі комунікацій у посиленні конкурентоспроможності та формуванні довіри. Результати дослідження свідчать, що ефективна комунікаційна система є умовою сервісної сталості та розвитку підприємств б'юти-індустрії.

Ключові слова: організаційні комунікації; сервісна модель, індустрія краси, клієнтський досвід, стандартизація сервісу, брендова ідентичність, адаптивність персоналу

Niameshchuk H.V., Krupskiy O.P., Stasiuk Yu.M. The Role of Organisational Communications in the Development of the Service Business Model in the Beauty Industry. Review article.

The article examines the role of organisational communications as a factor in developing the service business model in the beauty industry. It highlights the importance of internal and external communication in ensuring high-quality customer interaction, maintaining the stability of service processes, and supporting brand identity. The study identifies major communication impacts, including service standardisation, alignment of information flows, employee adaptability, and personalised customer experience. Emphasis is placed on the strategic role of communication in strengthening competitiveness and building trust. The findings indicate that an effective communication system is a prerequisite for service sustainability and business development in the beauty industry.

Keywords: organisational communications, service model, beauty industry, customer experience, service standardization, brand identity, employee adaptability

The modern beauty industry is rapidly transforming under the influence of digitalisation, growing competition and changing consumer expectations, which has been particularly evident in the post-pandemic recovery of the service sector in Ukraine [1]. The main feature of this industry is high competition, which constantly tests beauty industry companies on the quality of their services [2]. In such conditions, effective organisational communication is increasingly considered not as a secondary tool for supporting business processes, but as a strategic component of the service model of enterprise management [3, 4]. In the service sector, which has recently been forced to focus on a high degree of emotional interaction with customers, the staff communication skills and the quality of internal information flows directly affect service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty [5]. The formation of a service business model requires an understanding not only of external marketing channels, but also of the deep integration of internal communications into the daily activities of an organisation. It is through organisational communications that the coordination of employee actions, effective knowledge management, the transmission of brand values and timely adaptation to changes in the market environment are ensured [6]. In the service business of the beauty industry, where every contact with a customer has an emotional charge, it is crucial not only the content of messages, but also the form of their transmission, context and moment of interaction [7].

Research into organisational communications in the beauty business requires an interdisciplinary approach that combines managerial, marketing, psychological, and communicative aspects. Thus, within the framework of modern service concepts, communication is considered as a means of creating customer experience, building trust and laying the foundations for long-term relationships [8]. Particular attention is paid to adaptive communication models, which provide for personalisation of interaction, taking into account the individual characteristics of customers and the situational context. Despite the availability of empirical studies confirming the link between communication and service quality, there is no systematic analysis in the scientific literature of organisational communications as a factor in the strategic development of the service business model in the beauty industry. It is the gap that determines the relevance of theoretical research aimed at generalising scientific approaches to the role of communication in the organisational environment of service entrepreneurship.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Organisational communication is a key element in the formation of a service business model, especially in the beauty industry, where interaction with the customer has a pronounced emotional charge. The theory of sense-making assumes that an organisation functions as a space for collective understanding of situations arising in a dynamic market environment [9]. This is particularly relevant for the salon business, where flexibility in decision-making regarding communication policy is critical to maintaining a sustainable image and customer trust [10]. The role of management is not only to convey information but also to create conditions that ensure understanding and adaptation of messages within the organisational environment [11].

Within the framework of a systematic approach, it is emphasised that communication ensures the adaptability and stability of organisations, acting as a means of coordination between the functional elements of an enterprise [12]. It is the effectiveness of internal and external communication that allows businesses in the beauty industry to respond promptly to customer expectations, improving service quality and satisfaction levels [3]. The service quality in the beauty industry is inextricably linked to internal communication processes. Insufficient internal information sharing, a lack of standards for message exchange, and inconsistency in communication channels can lead to a decline in customer loyalty [12]. On the other hand, effective interpersonal communication, particularly in the form of feedback, supports both the organisational culture of the enterprise [14] and the service culture, which creates positive emotional impressions and lays the foundation for the formation of the brand's emotional capital [15]. A customer's emotional experience in a beauty salon not only determines the level of satisfaction but also ensures the formation of lasting advantages for a particular establishment [16].

In the practice of service companies, adaptive communication strategies are becoming increasingly popular, which involve personalisation of interaction,

consideration of consumer psychographic characteristics, and multi-channel communication [17]. Especially in the beauty industry, where customer sensitivity to non-verbal cues and emotional nuances is exceptionally high, it is essential to build an atmosphere of trust and support through thoughtful and well-designed service communication [18]. Organisational communication in the beauty industry not only plays an operational role but is also one of the key elements of the service business model. The systematic integration of communication strategies into personnel management, customer experience, and branding enables the formation of long-term relationships that support the company's sustainable competitiveness.

In light of these theoretical provisions and the specific nature of service interaction within the beauty industry, it is essential to clarify how organizational communications facilitate the creation of customer experience. Furthermore, it is necessary to examine how these communications ensure the strategic stability of the service business model, particularly given the high emotional labor involved in service delivery and rising consumer expectations. The issue of managerial flexibility is especially pertinent in today's volatile service market, a necessity corroborated by recent studies on adaptive strategic planning within small-scale beauty enterprises [19].

The study is based on systemic and interdisciplinary approaches that allow for the integration of managerial, communication, and behavioural aspects of the analysis of service interaction in the beauty industry. The methodological basis is a combination of conceptual analysis of scientific sources, interpretative understanding of organisational communication models and logical-semantic structuring of the service business model in the context of emotionally charged consumption.

The conclusions are based on an analytical review of relevant empirical and conceptual studies published in scientific journals in recent years, which made it possible to identify the key characteristics of effective communication interaction in service companies. A retrospective analysis of cases from leading companies in the beauty industry, in particular franchise chains such as G.Bar, LAVS, and Women Place, was used as an illustrative basis for testing the validity of theoretical propositions. These companies are representative examples of implementing the innovative customer experience models, where communication is a basic tool for creating added value for a service product. This analysis was conducted on the basis of open communication artifacts, including brand books, internal communication policies, service procedure descriptions, and public standards for speech and corporate style

Generalisations were formed through deductive reconstruction of the logic of the impact of organisational communication on the qualitative parameters of the service model: service standardisation, adaptability of interaction, stability of customer experience and strategic consistency of the enterprise. At the final stage of the study, a modelling method was used to structure generalised conclusions

in the form of typologies of communication forms, functions and corresponding management effects.

The main part

The analysis of theoretical sources and management approaches to service interaction in the beauty industry allowed us to formulate a research question that involves identifying the mechanisms through which organisational communication influences the construction and development of a service business model. Given the specifics of emotional consumption characteristic of the beauty industry, communication within an organisation is considered not only as a tool for transmitting information, but also as a socio-psychological resource that ensures the coordination of staff actions, the stability of the service experience and the support of brand identity. This section provides a step-by-step structuring of the results of theoretical analysis with a focus on four main dimensions: the nature of organisational communication, its impact on service standardisation, the role of adaptive interaction, and the link between communication and the strategic development of the service model. The discussion is based on an interdisciplinary approach that combines concepts of management communication, service marketing, and behavioural economics.

The nature of organisational communication in service enterprises in the beauty industry.

The findings from the theoretical literature review and practical observations of beauty industry enterprises suggest that organisational communication in this field is characterized by a high degree of operational saturation, yet lacks sufficient strategic reflection. In typical beauty service enterprises, vertical communication between managers and staff remains dominant, focusing primarily on functional instructions and the strict monitoring of service standard implementation [3]. Horizontal communication between employees is mainly situational and is rarely supported institutionally through internal procedures or a culture of openness.

At the level of interpersonal interaction, service quality depends significantly on the ability of staff to adapt their communicative behaviour to the individual style, requirements, and emotional state of the customer. However, such intuitive personalisation often occurs in spite of, rather than because of, organizational policies. These policies typically either fail to regulate these nuanced interactions or simplify them into rigid, formal service training protocols [16]. This leads to inconsistency in the service experience, which in turn reduces the predictability of service quality and potentially affects customer loyalty.

Within modern approaches to service management, organisational communication is interpreted as a mechanism for aligning employee behaviour with the brand's mission and values [11]. In beauty industry companies, this communication is often complicated by the lack of stable communication channels, insufficient feedback from line staff to management, and gaps in internal information logistics. As a result, employees who interact directly with customers do not

always convey the expected brand narrative and, therefore, do not ensure a consistent emotional impression from contact with the service.

Data obtained from the previous authors' research, as well as the results of analytical analysis of cases such as G.Bar, Women Place, BrowBar, and Queen Bee, demonstrate that positive examples of service communication are based on a combination of internal transparency, decentralised decision-making, and clear standards of social interaction [19-21]. Thus, the assumption about the connection between high-quality internal communication and the stability of the service model in the beauty business is confirmed in practice.

The impact of internal communication on service standardisation and customer satisfaction

One of the characteristic features of the service business in the beauty industry is the heterogeneity of the customer experience, which is often caused by the variability of staff communication behaviour. The lack of clear internal communication procedures leads to differences in the perception of service standards, which negatively affects the predictability of service and reduces customer satisfaction [12]. Empirical studies within the hairdressing sector confirm that clearly defined service protocols and visit standards directly correlate with customer satisfaction levels and the rate of repeat patronage [23]. The companies that ensure a high degree of consistency in communication processes demonstrate more stable service quality indicators and a higher level of consumer trust [15].

Internal communication in service companies performs not only an informative function, but also a normative one – it conveys brand values, sets the framework for acceptable behaviour, and forms a common understanding of the essence of "quality service" among employees [11]. It is through daily exchanges of messages, feedback, internal instructions and informal communication practices that service interaction standards are implemented. In the beauty industry, where high levels of emotional engagement are standard, even minor deviations from expected behavioral norms can significantly erode customer loyalty and lead to a decline in retention [18].

Research shows that well-structured internal communication ensures service reproducibility, which is considered a key condition for standardisation in the context of personalised service [3]. At the same time, standards are not limited to procedural checklists, but include communication scenarios, emotional scripts, and behaviour models that are formed within the organisational culture [22]. In this case, internal communication acts as a mechanism for socialising new employees, supporting existing practices, and integrating service orientation into daily interactions.

It is noteworthy that in the case of companies with a strong communication circuit (e.g., G.Bar, LAVS, or Women Place), customers not only receive the expected level of service but also feel a sense of shared values that are conveyed at every stage of contact, from the initial meeting to after-sales support [20, 21]. Internal communication here acts as a cementing factor that combines the service strategy with specific actions of the staff. The effectiveness of internal

communication in the beauty industry's service business not only determines the quality of the company's current operations but also forms the basis for long-term customer loyalty and stable growth. Its strategic importance lies in ensuring service consistency in the face of growing emotional expectations from consumers.

The role of communication adaptability in shaping a personalised customer experience.

Personalisation of service in the beauty industry is based not only on the individual selection of procedures or stylistic decisions, but, above all, on the ability of staff to adapt their communication behaviour to the psychological and social characteristics of the customer. Research in the field of service marketing confirms that personalised interactions are a key factor in developing long-term customer relationships and increasing loyalty [24]. Adaptive communication is interpreted as a managerial competence that allows one to respond effectively to verbal and non-verbal signals and change the tone of interaction depending on consumer needs and situational context [16]. It is these abilities that provide a sense of individual approach, which is one of the key factors of loyalty in a highly competitive service environment. The importance of non-verbal communication in the salon business is confirmed by empirical studies that demonstrate the direct impact of the master's non-verbal behaviour on customer satisfaction and the likelihood of revisiting the establishment [25].

Adaptive communication is closely linked to an employee's emotional intelligence, which contemporary research recognises as a fundamental prerequisite for effective work in customer service [18]. This refers not only to the ability to identify the customer's emotional state, but also to the ability to respond appropriately, maintain the desired atmosphere of interaction, and, if necessary, change the communication scenario without damaging the overall perception of the service. The ability to adapt the service to the individual expectations of the customer is considered a strategic factor in building long-term relationships [26]. In beauty industry companies, this is reflected in the details: intonation, body language, communication rhythm, even pauses – all of these become tools for influencing the customer experience.

Examples of effective adaptation of communication strategies at the organisational level deserve special attention. For example, in some cases, chain salons use internal customer maps – tools that allow staff to form preliminary ideas about the customer's style and needs based on previous visits, collected feedback and CRM systems. This, in turn, reduces the time needed for mutual adjustment and lowers tension in the first phase of interaction [11]. Adaptive communication transforms from an individual skill into an element of a service strategy embedded in organisational procedures. At the same time, it should be noted that excessive standardisation of communication may contradict the principles of personalisation. The balance between the given communication framework and the flexibility to respond to individual customer requests is achieved

through the development of second-order competencies – reflexivity, situational thinking, and empathy. It is these qualities that are increasingly being identified as targets in staff training programmes at leading salons [12].

In summary, adaptive communication in the service environment of the beauty industry serves not only to correct behaviour but also to convey to the customer a message about their uniqueness, importance and involvement in the interaction process. A personalised communication experience that takes context into account increases the likelihood of repeat visits, contributes to the formation of the brand's emotional capital and is an indicator of the maturity of the service business model.

Organisational communication as a factor in the strategic development of the service model.

In today's service business, organisational communication is increasingly seen as a strategic function that affects not only operational efficiency but also the long-term viability of the company. This is especially true for companies in the beauty industry, where competitiveness is determined not only by product range or price parameters, but also by the depth of emotional connection with the customer, the stability of service impressions, and the brand's reputation capitalisation [3].

The strategic role of communication is to convey the organisation's mission and values at all levels of interaction, both internal and external. Communication becomes a tool for aligning goals, interpreting changes, adapting to market conditions and strengthening brand identity [11]. In the beauty industry, this manifests itself in the organisation's ability to maintain the integrity of the customer experience regardless of staff, location changes or external challenges, including post-pandemic ones [1]. The way organisational communication allows companies to identify new customer expectations and respond quickly to them is also of managerial importance. Studies emphasise that organisations with a high level of communicative sensitivity demonstrate better results in customer retention, service model scaling, and social responsibility strategy implementation [18]. This is especially important for small businesses in the service sector, where resources are limited and customer loyalty is often the only stabilising factor.

Examples of effective communication strategies include the practices of network service brands, such as G.Bar, where service standards and values are systematically communicated through multiple channels, from brand books and training platforms to visual interior elements and staff communication standards [27]. Such practices not only ensure service stability but also allow businesses to scale up without losing quality and customer focus. Organisational communication in the beauty industry service business is not just a channel for transmitting instructions, but a key asset of the enterprise that determines its adaptability, reputational stability, capacity for innovation and strategic growth. Its integration into the business model at all levels – from daily interactions to

brand positioning – is a determining factor in service consistency and long-term success.

Summary of communication factors affecting service efficiency in the beauty industry.

A systematisation of the material presented above allows for the identification of the key organisational communication forms and an analysis of their impact on service business models within the beauty industry. Regardless of management styles, business formats, or target audience characteristics, certain communication elements remain critical to delivering a high-quality, coordinated, and personalized service experience.

Table 1 presents a typology of communication forms used within a service enterprise, along with the corresponding management functions and expected results. This typology allows for identifying both the immediate operational effect (e.g., improved internal coordination) and the strategic impact (support for service identity, stability of customer experience).

Complementing the functional dimension, Table 2 examines specific communication factors that directly affect the service model's effectiveness. The presented pairs of "factor – management function – risk in case of absence" allow for the visualisation of both the advantages of active management of communication processes and the consequences of ignoring these aspects in daily practice.

Summarising the analysis results of theoretical approaches and practical cases, a generalised model was proposed that demonstrates the relationship between key forms of organisational communication, expected management results, and the strategic effectiveness of the service business model (Fig. 1).

The model illustrates the relationship between organisational communication as a management category and key parameters of the service model in the beauty industry.

Table 1. Interrelationship between Forms of Organisational Communication and Key Service Outcomes

Form of communication	Description	Impact on the service model
Vertical (top management)	Instructions, orders, brand policies	Forms standards, but is often perceived as formal
Horizontal (colleagues)	Daily coordination of actions, exchange of information	Determines operational coordination
Feedback (internal)	Internal surveys, feedback from employees	Increases the accuracy of adaptation to market needs
Adaptive communication	Personalised customer interaction	Strengthens emotional connection and loyalty
Strategic brand communication	Brand book, scripts, service manuals	Ensures service consistency and scalability

Source: authors' own elaboration

Table 2. Communication Factors for a Successful Service Model in the Beauty Industry

Communication factor	Function in the service model	Risks in the absence of the factor
Consistency of internal communications	Service standardisation	Variability of service experience
Availability of feedback channels	Updating procedures in line with reality	Loss of relevance of standards
Adaptability of staff	Personalisation of interaction	Formalisation of contact, loss of empathy
Communication culture	Support for service values	Degradation of customer experience
Brand transmission through communication	Building long-term loyalty	Blurring of brand identity

Source: authors' own elaboration

Figure 1. A Model of the Impact of Organisational Communication on Beauty Industry Business Models

Source: authors' own elaboration

Organisational communication occupies a central place in the structure, acting as a channel for communicating internal policies, brand values, and individualised influences. It functions as a tool for aligning expectations, setting standards, and ensuring service consistency. On the one hand, effective communication supports service standardisation, staff adaptability, and emotional interaction with the customer. On the other hand, it serves as the basis for building trust, increasing customer loyalty, and long-term business development. This model allows for the conceptualisation of communication not only as a supporting process but also as a systemic mechanism in service entrepreneurship.

The development of a service business model in the beauty industry largely depends on the coordination of communication processes, the ability of staff to adapt their interaction with customers, and the strategic integrity of brand identity. Based on the theoretical analysis presented above, as well as taking into account the specifics of emotional consumption inherent in the beauty sphere, the authors propose a conceptual model of organisational communications. The model systematises key forms of communication and

demonstrates how their interaction shapes the stability of the service model and the strategic consistency of the enterprise.

The proposed model is based on a three-level communication structure – internal, interactive and interpretative levels, which reflect the underlying mechanisms of customer experience formation. This approach allows for the integration of operational, interpersonal, and value aspects of interaction, revealing communication as a system-forming element of service entrepreneurship (Fig. 2).

The Internal Communication Layer defines the organisational discipline of information flows and ensures consistency in staff actions. Its key elements include: service communication standards and policies (interaction scenarios (scripts), checklists, brand language style); internal instructions, service manuals and regulations; coordination and information support channels (CRM, internal chats, knowledge management platforms); training programmes and instruction in communicative behaviour. At this level, service implementation stability is formed, which minimises behavioural variability and reduces the risks of uneven service quality.

Figure 2. A Conceptual Model of Organisational Communication within the Beauty Industry Service Sector

Source: authors' own elaboration

The Interactive Communication Layer reflects the direct interaction between staff and customers, which is highly emotionally charged and largely determines the subjective perception of the service. The key components of the interactive level include: staff emotional intelligence; adaptive communicative behaviour; the ability to respond to individual customer characteristics; and skills in conveying empathy, attention and support. It is the interactive level that is responsible for forming the emotional capital of the brand, which is a key factor in loyalty in the beauty industry.

The Interpretive Communication Layer reflects the deep meaning structures that form the overall brand identity and set the framework for the perception of service interaction. This level of communication includes: brand values and service philosophy; corporate style and brand book; service narrative, stories, rituals, and symbols; communication messages aimed at building trust. At this level, communication ensures the integrity of the customer experience and lays the foundation for long-term competitiveness.

The coordinated interaction of three levels forms the communication architecture of the enterprise, which determines service quality, customer loyalty, and scalability. Internal mechanisms ensure predictability of actions, interactive mechanisms ensure emotional appeal, and interpretive mechanisms ensure strategic brand integrity. Communication plays a dual role: operational (coordination, standards, processes) and strategic (values, loyalty, emotional experience). The proposed model allows for the generalisation of these characteristics and presents communication as a multi-level system that influences the service performance indicators of the enterprise.

The generalisations presented in Tables 1, 2 and Figures 1, 2 not only summarise analytical observations but also enable the structuring of a service enterprise's communication space as a multi-level system with specific functional and strategic outcomes. This, in turn, provides a foundation for developing practical recommendations and conducting further empirical research in the field of management communications within the service economy.

Conclusions

As a result of the conducted research, it was found that organisational communication plays a key role in the formation, maintenance and development of the service business model in the beauty industry. It functions as an inter-level management mechanism that ensures consistency in staff actions, standardisation of service, flexibility in customer interactions and strategic stability of the enterprise. In an industry where every point of contact has an emotional impact, effective communication becomes a critical resource that shapes customer expectations and determines their experience with the brand.

The analysed sources and case studies show that the service efficiency of companies in the beauty industry depends on four interrelated factors: the nature of internal communication, the availability of standardisation mechanisms, the level of staff adaptability, and the strategic transmission of brand values. All these components are formed and maintained through targeted organisational communication. The use of its tools – from brand books to personalised interaction

scenarios – allows not only to maintain a stable level of service, but also to adapt the business to changing consumer expectations.

A generalised typology of forms and functions of organisational communication, as well as a visual model, demonstrates that the service consistency of a beauty industry enterprise is the result of the harmonious interaction of the operational, emotional and strategic components of communication. This makes it possible to view communication not as an auxiliary administrative process but as a strategically significant component of a service enterprise's business model. The results of the study are of theoretical and practical importance for the further development of tools for assessing the quality of organisational communication, as well as for improving management practices in the service sector, focused on a high level of customer emotional engagement. In the future, it seems advisable to expand the research in the direction of an empirical study of the relationship between the communication structure of an enterprise and customer loyalty indicators in various segments of the beauty industry.

Abstract

The article provides a comprehensive examination of organisational communications as a determining factor in the development and strengthening of the service business model within the beauty industry. Amid growing digitalisation, rising customer expectations, and intensifying competition in service markets, communication processes are emerging as a core strategic instrument rather than a secondary managerial tool. Effective communication enables companies to enhance service quality, maintain consistency across customer interactions, and reinforce brand identity in emotionally charged service environments. As the beauty sector becomes increasingly dependent on personalised, trust-based client relationships, the integration of structured, adaptive, and multidirectional communication emerges as a crucial strategic instrument for sustaining customer loyalty and long-term competitiveness.

The study is grounded in a conceptual and systematic examination of contemporary scholarly literature published between 2021 and 2025, encompassing research in service management, organisational behaviour, marketing communications, and behavioural economics. Its analytical foundation integrates peer-reviewed publications, industry case studies, policy papers, and communication frameworks pertinent to service-oriented enterprises. Particular emphasis is placed on empirical cases from leading beauty service brands, including G.Bar, LAVS, Women Place, and BrowBar, which offer demonstrative evidence of how communication systems shape customer experience and sustain operational stability. These cases elucidate the mechanisms through which internal communication, brand-mediated messaging, and adaptive interpersonal interaction collectively ensure coherent, consistent, and predictable service delivery.

The research identifies four core communication dimensions that influence service performance in beauty enterprises: internal communication structures, service standardisation processes, staff adaptability and emotional intelligence, and brand-aligned strategic communication. Internal communication ensures coordinated workflow and alignment of informational flows, enabling employees to deliver stable service quality. Standardised communication scripts and behavioural models reduce service variability and enhance customer satisfaction. At the interpersonal level, adaptive communication supported by emotional intelligence facilitates personalisation and strengthens the emotional engagement that underpins client loyalty in beauty services. Strategic communication, expressed through brand books, linguistic standards, and visual identity guidelines, ensures continuity of the customer experience across touchpoints and supports business scalability.

From a managerial perspective, the article emphasises that organisational communication functions as a mechanism for embedding service values, shaping organisational culture, and ensuring service resilience. Communication plays a central role in creating a shared understanding of service norms, building trust among employees, and supporting the implementation of innovative service practices. Leadership involvement is essential for cultivating a culture of openness, feedback, and client-centred thinking. Moreover, communication-sensitive management enables rapid adaptation to market changes, effective crisis response, and high-quality service recovery.

The study also addresses common challenges faced by beauty service companies, including fragmented communication flows, limited feedback channels, inconsistencies in employee communication behaviour, and insufficient integration of communication standards into daily operations. These issues can undermine customer

loyalty, weaken brand identity, and lead to significant service variability. Overcoming such barriers requires the development of communication competencies, the implementation of multichannel communication tools, and the alignment of service scripts with organisational values and customer expectations. Emotionally intelligent communication practices also contribute to managing client sensitivity, preventing conflicts, and enhancing service empathy – an essential component of value creation in beauty services.

Furthermore, the analysis highlights the importance of cross-functional communication for implementing service innovations, integrating digital tools, and supporting omnichannel service strategies. As the beauty industry moves toward hybrid service ecosystems that combine offline experiences with digital customer journeys, communication becomes the key integrator of technology adoption, CRM systems, and personalised service processes. Communication-enabled knowledge sharing and internal transparency form the foundation for scalable and sustainable service models.

Overall, the article concludes that organisational communication is a strategic asset that shapes service quality, customer experience, and competitive positioning in the beauty industry. Its role extends far beyond information exchange, functioning as a system-forming component of service design, operational coordination, and emotional value creation. The findings contribute to the broader discourse on communication-driven service management and offer practical implications for managers seeking to enhance service stability, brand loyalty, and organisational effectiveness in the rapidly evolving beauty services sector.

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